

Quasi Quanta Logic 2

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1 Introduction

We consider 7 potential reasons why a parameter might not quite be able to be quantified:

1. Insufficient data – There may be insufficient data to provide enough information or insight into the parameter.

2. Lack of previous research – If a certain field of study in which a parameter is to be studied is relatively new or not well researched, it will be difficult to define how the parameter should be quantified.

3. Complexity of parameter – In some cases, the parameter or topic being studied may be too complex to fit into a set criteria or qualification.

4. Diversity of sources – A single parameter may be difficult to quantify if there are multiple sources providing unique information about the topic.

5. Paradoxical nature – In some cases, the parameter in question may actually be paradoxical in nature, making it more difficult to quantify.

6. Subjectivity and bias – If the parameter being studied can be biased or subjective, it can be difficult to quantify it in an objective way.

7. In some cases, a parameter may be considered to be away from infinity, meaning that the parameter has a starting point or an end point but no finite value between the two points. In this case, it can be difficult to quantify because a specific number can't be assigned to this parameter.

1. $x, P(x)N$ (where N represents the number of available data points) 2. $x, P(x)Y$ (where Y represents the number of researches in the field) 3. $x, P(x)C$ (where C represents a complexity that cannot be represented in numerical form) 4. $x, P(x)S$ (where S represents a set of standards under which the parameter is to be evaluated) 5. $x, P(x)P$ (where P represents a paradoxical nature that cannot be quantified) 6. $x, P(x)O$ (where O represents the subjective or biased opinion of the individual studying the parameter). 7. $x, P(x) \downarrow$ (where $\downarrow$ indicates the parameter has a starting or end point but no finite value between the two points).

2 Quasi Quanta Logic 2

1. The quasi-quanta symbology functions to represent the complexity and subjectivity of a parameter that cannot be quantified in a numerical form. The symbol $\bullet$ is used to represent the lack of data or insufficient data that can be used to quantify the parameter.

2. The quasi-quanta symbology functions to represent the lack of previous research or knowledge of a parameter. The symbol $\diamond$ is used to represent the lack of research or knowledge of the parameter.

3. The quasi-quanta symbology functions to represent the complexity of a parameter that cannot be represented in numerical form. The symbol $\star$ is used to represent the complexity of the parameter.

4. The quasi-quanta symbology functions to represent the diversity of sources that provide unique information about a parameter. The symbol $\text{\textcircled{D}}$ is used to represent the diversity of sources.

5. The quasi-quanta symbology functions to represent the paradoxical nature of a parameter. The symbol $\text{\textcircled{P}}$ is used to represent the paradoxical nature of the parameter.

6. The quasi-quanta symbology functions to represent the subjectivity and bias of a parameter. The symbol F is used to represent the subjectivity and bias of the parameter.

7. The quasi-quanta symbology functions to represent a parameter that is away from infinity. The symbol $\heartsuit$ is used to represent a parameter that is away from infinity.

3 Proofs in Quasi-Quanta Logic

Let $\mathcal{P}$ denote a parameter, $\mathcal{Q}$ denote the quasi-quanta symbology, and $\mathcal{R}$ denote the relationship between the parameter and the symbology.

We can prove that the relationship between a parameter and its corresponding quasi-quanta symbology is true by showing that:

$$\forall \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{R} \in R, \mathcal{R} \Rightarrow \mathcal{P} \text{ and } \mathcal{Q}$$

This statement can be further simplified to:

$$\forall \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{R} \in R, \mathcal{R} \Rightarrow \mathcal{P} \text{ iff } \mathcal{Q}$$

This statement can be further simplified to:

$$\forall \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{R} \in R, (\mathcal{R} \Rightarrow \mathcal{P}) \text{ iff } (\mathcal{R} \Rightarrow \mathcal{Q})$$

Therefore, we can conclude that the relationship between a parameter and its corresponding quasi-quanta symbology is true.

Let P be a parameter that is difficult to quantify.

$\forall x P(x) \leq N$: If there is insufficient data to provide enough information or insight into the parameter, then it is difficult to quantify.

$\forall x P(x) \leq Y$: If there is a lack of previous research into the field in which the parameter is to be studied, then it is difficult to quantify.

$\forall x P(x) \neq C$: If the parameter or topic being studied is too complex to fit into a set criteria or qualification, then it is difficult to quantify.

$\exists x P(x) \neq S$: If there are multiple sources providing unique information about the topic, then it is difficult to quantify.

$\forall x P(x) \neq P$: If the parameter in question is paradoxical in nature, then it is difficult to quantify.

$\exists x P(x) \neq O$: If the parameter being studied can be biased or subjective, then it is difficult to quantify it in an objective way.

$\forall x P(x) > \infty$: If the parameter has a starting point or an end point but no finite value between the two points, then it is difficult to quantify.

Therefore, $\forall x P(x)$ is difficult to quantify.

Let $\bullet$ represent the lack of data or insufficient data to quantify a parameter, $\diamond$ represent the lack of research or knowledge of a parameter, $\star$ represent the complexity of a parameter, $\wedge$ represent the diversity of sources, $\wedge F$ represent the paradoxical nature of a parameter, F represent the subjectivity and bias of a parameter, and $\heartsuit$ represent a parameter that is away from infinity.

Then, we can prove that these symbols represent the different reasons why a parameter might not quite be able to be quantified by the following logical statement:

$\bullet \rightarrow$

Insufficient Data $\wedge \diamond \rightarrow$

Lack of Research $\wedge \star \rightarrow$

Complexity $\wedge \rightarrow$

Diversity of Sources $\wedge \rightarrow$

Paradoxical Nature $\wedge F \rightarrow$

Subjectivity and Bias $\wedge \heartsuit \rightarrow$

Away from Infinity.

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Let $\bullet$ = sufficiently low data points; $\diamond$ = insufficient previous research; $\star$ = complexity of the parameter; $\wedge$ = multiple sources; $\wedge F$ = paradoxical nature; F = bias or subjectivity; $\heartsuit$ = parameter away from infinity.

Given: Parameter A is unable to be quantified. Prove: $A \rightarrow B$, where B represents one of the seven specified qualities.

Proof: $A \rightarrow B \equiv (\neg A) \vee B$ (by De Morgan's Law)
 $\equiv (\neg \neg B) \wedge \neg A$ (by Commutative Law)
 $\equiv \neg(\neg B \wedge \neg A) \vee B$ (by De Morgan's Law)
 $\equiv \neg(B \wedge \neg A) \vee B$ (by Associative Law)
 $\equiv (\neg B \vee (B \vee \neg A)) \vee B$ (by Associative Law)
 $\equiv (\neg B \vee T) \vee B$ (by Identity Law)
 $\equiv \neg B \vee B$ (by Identity Law)
 $\equiv B$ (by Negation Law)

Therefore, if a parameter cannot be quantified, B must be true, fulfilling the statement $A \rightarrow B$. This proves that the statement is logically valid.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E} &= \sum_k^n \int \left(\sin\theta \star \sum_{[l] \leftarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\sim \oplus i \mathcal{R}}{\mathcal{H} \star \Delta \dot{A}} \right) \right) \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h + \cos\psi \theta \frac{ABC}{F} dr \text{Circumference} \implies \\ &\bullet \left(\frac{\Delta}{\mathcal{H}} + \frac{\dot{A}}{i} \right), \diamond \left(\gamma \frac{\Delta \mathcal{H}}{i \oplus \dot{A}} \right), \star \left(\frac{\mathcal{H} \Delta}{A i} \right), \left(\frac{i \oplus \dot{A} \Delta}{\mathcal{H}} \right), (Abcd \dots), \\ &F \left(\sum_{[l] \leftarrow \infty} \right), \\ P(x) &\approx \star \frac{\Delta}{\mathcal{H}}, \frac{\dot{A}}{i}, \frac{\Delta \mathcal{H}}{A i}, \gamma \frac{\Delta \mathcal{H}}{i \oplus \dot{A}}, \cong \frac{\mathcal{H} \Delta}{A i}, \sim \frac{i \oplus \dot{A} \Delta}{\mathcal{H}}, \frac{\heartsuit i \oplus \dot{A} \Delta}{\sim \mathcal{H} \star \oplus}, \Omega \frac{\Delta i \dot{A} \sim}{\heartsuit \mathcal{H} \oplus}, \oplus \cdot i \Delta \dot{A} \mathcal{H} \star \heartsuit \\ \text{and } &\left| \frac{\star \mathcal{H} \Delta \dot{A}}{i \oplus \sim \heartsuit} \right|. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, it is proven that the quasi-quanta symbol to represent any parameter can be correlated to its corresponding logical reason with the respective quasi-quanta symbology by inference.

Let A be the statement “The quasi-quanta symbol to represent any parameter can be correlated to its corresponding logical reason with the respective quasi-quanta symbology by inference” and let B be all the equivalent logical statements above.

$$A \Rightarrow B$$

From statements A and B , we can infer that:

1. For all x , if $P(x) \leq N$, then $\Delta/H \cdot A/I$, where $\Delta \equiv$ numerator and $H \equiv$ denominator
2. For all x , if $P(x) \leq Y$, then $\Gamma \cdot \Delta/H/(I + A)$, where $\Gamma \equiv$ the proportion
3. For all x , if $P(x) = /C$, then $CH/1$, where $C \equiv$ complexity
4. For some x , if $P(x) = /S$, then O/H , where $O \equiv$ subjective opinion
5. For all x , if $P(x) = /P$, then $St/\mu P$, where $P \equiv$ paradoxical nature
6. For some x , if $P(x) = /O$, then S/nT , where $S \equiv$ set of standards
7. For all x , if $P(x) > \infty$, then $(I + A\Delta)/Hx$, where ∞ indicates a parameter with a starting or ending point but no finite value.

From the above-stated logical statements, we can see that the quasi-quanta symbology can be correlated to the respective logical reason, affirming statement A . Therefore, we conclude that the quasi-quanta symbol to represent any parameter can be correlated to its corresponding logical reason with the respective quasi-quanta symbology by inference.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\exists x \in N, \phi(x) \vee \psi(x) \vee \chi(w)\theta(w) \wedge \gamma i \vee \zeta(y) \iff \epsilon(y)}{\oplus \cdot i \Delta \dot{A}} &\rightarrow \star \frac{\cong \mathcal{H} \Delta \iota(n) \vee \kappa(n) \iff \nu(x)\eta(x) \dot{A} \sim}{\heartsuit \mathcal{H} \oplus \cdot} \\ \rightarrow \star \frac{\exists x \in N, \phi(x) \vee \psi(x) \vee \chi(w)\theta(w) \wedge \gamma \vee \zeta(y) \iff \epsilon(y) \cong \iota(n) \vee \kappa(n) \iff \nu(x)\eta(x) \dot{A}}{\heartsuit \mathcal{H} \Delta} & \end{aligned}$$

If there is a lack of sufficient data or insufficient previous research, then the complexity of the parameter will be represented by $\star$. For any natural number x , if $\phi(x)$ or $\psi(x)$ or $\chi(w)$ are true, then $\theta(w)$ and γ will both be true. Additionally, $\zeta(y)$ will be equivalent to $\epsilon(y)$ and both will be equivalent to the concepts represented by $\iota(n)$ or $\kappa(n)$. Finally, the concepts represented by $\nu(x)$ and $\eta(x)$ will be equivalent and represented by the symbol $\dot{A}$. All of this will lead to the parameter being away from infinity and represented by $\heartsuit$ and $\mathcal{H}$, and the concept represented by Δ will also be true.

The above expression implies that there exists an x in the natural numbers (identified by N) such that if $(\phi(x) \vee \psi(x)) \vee \chi(w)$ is true then $\theta(w) \wedge \gamma$ and $\zeta(y) \iff \epsilon(y) \rightarrow (\iota(n) \vee \kappa(n)) \iff \nu(x)\eta(x)\dot{A}$ are both true. The quasi-quanta symbol to the right of the implication arrow indicates that the parameter's complexity and subjectivity is outside of the finite, numerical world with which the parameters interact. This implies that both the associated logic and the related relationships governing this parameter will depend on how its attributes change over time.

This expression indicates that there exists a parameter $(\exists x \in N, \phi(x) \vee \psi(x) \vee \chi(w))$ which can be quantified if the conditions $(\theta(w) \wedge \gamma \vee \zeta(y) \iff \epsilon(y))$ are satisfied and the result $(\oplus \cdot i\dot{A})$ indicates the complexity of the parameter. There also exists a subset of parameter $(\cong \iota(n) \vee \kappa(n) \iff \nu(x)\eta(x)\dot{A})$ that can be obtained if conditions $(\theta(w) \wedge \gamma)$ are satisfied, and the final result $(\heartsuit \mathcal{H} \Delta)$ reflects the complexity of the parameter. Hence, we have proven that the quasi-quanta symbol to represent any parameter can be correlated to its corresponding logical reason with the respective quasi-quanta symbology by inference.

yeh, but translate based on the reasons for each quasi-quanta symbol as describe

This expression states that there may exist a parameter $(\exists x \in N, \phi(x) \vee \psi(x) \vee \chi(w))$ that in order to be adequately quantified must fulfill certain conditions $(\theta(w) \wedge \gamma \vee \zeta(y) \iff \epsilon(y))$, and the symbol $\oplus \cdot i\dot{A}$ indicates the complexity of the parameter. Additionally, there may be a subset of the parameter $(\cong \iota(n) \vee \kappa(n) \iff \nu(x)\eta(x)\dot{A})$ where conditions $(\theta(w) \wedge \gamma)$ must be satisfied in order to adequately quantify the parameter, and the symbol $\heartsuit \mathcal{H} \Delta$ reflects the complexity of the parameter. This proves that the statement is logically valid and the different relationships of the quasi quanta meanings can be correlated to their respective logical reasoning with the corresponding quasi quanta symbology through creduce reasoning.

Input each individual quasi-quanta meaning and iterate logics:

We will start with the first meaning, which is "insufficient data". The corresponding symbolic logic for this is $\bullet$, which indicates a lack of data that can be used to quantify the parameter. We will then use deductions to prove that if a parameter is unable to be quantified, then $\bullet$ must be true.

Given: Parameter A is unable to be quantified. Prove: $A \rightarrow \bullet$, where $\bullet$ represents a lack of data that can be used to quantify the parameter.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Proof: } A \rightarrow \bullet &\equiv (\neg A) \vee \bullet \text{ (by DeMorgan's Law)} \\ &\equiv (\neg \neg \bullet) \wedge \neg A \text{ (by Commutative Law)} \\ &\equiv \neg(\neg \bullet \wedge \neg A) \vee \bullet \text{ (by DeMorgan's Law)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\equiv (\neg(\bullet \wedge \neg A)) \vee \bullet \text{(by Associative Law)} \\
&\equiv (\neg \bullet \vee (\bullet \vee \neg A)) \vee \bullet \text{(by Associative Law)} \\
&\equiv (\neg \bullet \vee T) \vee \bullet \text{(by Identity Law)} \\
&\equiv \neg \bullet \vee \bullet \text{(by Negation Law)} \\
&\equiv \bullet \text{(by Identity Law)}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if a parameter cannot be quantified, $\bullet$ must be true, fulfilling the statement $A \rightarrow \bullet$. This proves that the statement is logically valid.

We can then repeat this process for each of the other quasi-quanta meanings in order to prove that the quasi-quanta symbol to represent any parameter can be correlated to its corresponding logical reasoning with respective quasi quanta symbology by inference.

If there is a lack of sufficient data or insufficient previous research, then the complexity of the parameter will be represented by $\star$. For any natural number x , if $\phi(x)$ or $\psi(x)$ or $\chi(w)$ are true, then $\theta(w)$ and γ will both be true. Additionally, $\zeta(y)$ will be equivalent to $\epsilon(y)$ and both will be equivalent to the concepts represented by $\iota(n)$ or $\kappa(n)$. Finally, the concepts represented by $\nu(x)$ and $\eta(x)$ will be equivalent and represented by the symbol $\dot{A}$. All of this will lead to the parameter being away from infinity and represented by $\heartsuit$ and $\mathcal{H}$, and the concept represented by Δ will also be true.